

Uncovering Freight Flow Dynamics: A Data-Driven Approach Using Edge-Convolutional model

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Abstract: Freight vehicle trajectories play a critical role in urban logistics systems, reflecting operational efficiency and exhibiting strong correlations with urban transportation functionality and safety. While trajectory mining for freight vehicles has gained considerable attention across multiple research fields, key challenges remain to be concerned. Existing studies often rely on trajectory origin-destination (OD) network structures but neglect the semantic features of interaction networks. Additionally, conventional methods are usually designed based on static network models, which inadequately capture temporal dependencies among logistics activities. To address these gaps, this study proposes a novel spatial-temporal-semantic integrated framework based on spatial interaction network analysis. After identifying freight vehicle dwelling locations using spatiotemporal DBSCAN clustering, we construct a temporally ordered freight vehicle flow network incorporating dwelling duration, land use attributes, and spatial distribution patterns. An enhanced edge-convolutional network model is developed for spatiotemporal trajectory representation learning, and combined with spectral clustering to infer semantic patterns. Interpretable machine learning method is further applied to uncover spatiotemporal dynamics in distribution of freight vehicle travel flow. The case study is conducted with 110,000 freight vehicles in Shenzhen during one week (270 million GPS records). Clustering results reveal distinct spatiotemporal distributions for long- and short-duration dwelling behaviors and identify diverse freight vehicle travel semantics. Contrary to human mobility networks, clusters of freight vehicle dwelling locations are not necessarily spatially contiguous, with certain clusters exhibiting cross-district interaction patterns. These patterns strongly correlate with urban functional structures, particularly logistics facilities and hubs distribution. The proposed framework aids in understanding freight flow network dynamics and offers insights for optimizing spatiotemporal resource allocation in freight systems. The findings provide empirical evidence to guide logistics operations and urban freight infrastructure planning.

Keywords: Spatial interaction network; Truck trajectory; Spatial temporal mining; Graph convolution